

Mounting and preserving insects for scientific collections

A step by step tutorial

Foto Lisa Schäublin.

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Introduction

Museum specimens must be properly mounted and preserved before storing them in a collection. In entomology, dry conservation is generally used for more heavily sclerotized specimens. The most important steps of the procedure are here illustrated mostly for bush crickets and grasshoppers (Orthoptera).

Killing specimens

Quite often specimens are alive when they arrive at a Natural History Museum. Therefore the first step of the mounting procedure is killing the specimens. In entomology, there are several possibilities, which are explained below.

1) Killing with ethyl acetate

Place specimens in a container with vapour of ethyl acetate for 1–2 hours.

Preparation of the killing jar: Add a piece of cloth with a few drops of ethyl acetate to a 300–500 ml bottle (Attention: do not use bottles made of polystyrene or PVC bottles, only glass, polyethylene or polypropylene!). Add ethyl acetate each time the bottle is opened.

By treating the specimens with ethyl acetate, they remain supple and can be easily softened, even after years. The substance is relatively harmless.

Rigor mortis is less pronounced (e.g., compared with potassium cyanide).

About three to five hours after stuffing the specimens can be arranged without any problems.

Some colours may be sensitive to ethyl acetate, hence never let the specimens come in contact with the liquid. Specimens should only be put in vapour.

2) Killing with potassium cyanide

Place specimens in a jar with potassium cyanide (Fig. 1) for 1–2 hours.

Preparation of the killing jar: place 10–20 cyanide crystals into plaster in a 300–500 ml bottle, let plaster dry well, finished. The bottle can be used for several years. Ready-to-use cyanide jars are available for purchase.

Professionals use cyanide as a killing agent because it does not affect the often sensitive colours of the grasshoppers and crickets.

After killing, rigor mortis quickly sets in, which hinders mounting. Therefore, put specimens in the refrigerator and leave them overnight.

Attention: Potassium cyanide is very poisonous, therefore clearly label the killing jars and keep it under lock and key!

3) Other killing methods

Insects may also be put into a deep freeze (below -15°C), where they die quickly. However, some specimens may lose their appendages.

Specimens may also be killed by placing them directly in 70–90 % ethanol. This method is not suitable for larger specimens, which should be mounted dry later. It is also critical for specimens with sensitive colours (such as most bush crickets and grasshoppers or dragonflies) or specimens with fragile body parts (such as scales on the wings of butterflies and moths).

Fig. 1. A typical killing jar made from polyethylen. Foto Lisa Schäublin.

Mounting specimens on insect pins

Fig. 2A. Specimen of *Ehippiger terrestris*, stuffed and pinned. Foto Lisa Schäublin.

Fig. 2B. Specimen of *Arcyptera fusca*, pinned without stuffing. Foto Lisa Schäublin.

Larger or soft bodied specimens like bush-crickets (Fig. 2A) must be "stuffed". For smaller or hard bodied specimens like a grasshopper (Fig 2B) stuffing (steps 1-5) can be omitted. The following tools are useful to conserve a specimen (Fig. 3): Killing jar (1), hemp fibre (2), insect pins (3), card rectangles (4), dissecting instruments (5), pinning block (Etikettentreppe) (6), different types of mounting boards (7), water soluble glue (e.g., fish glue) and ethanol 60%.

Fig. 3. Materials used for stuffing and mounting. Foto Lisa Schäublin.

1) *Preparation of the stuffing material*

Hemp fibres (Fig. 4) are used for stuffing. They are cut to a length of about 1–2 mm. It is worth preparing the hemp for several preparations at once. 10–15 cm³ are enough for about 25–30 specimens. Hemp has the advantage that it hardly absorbs moisture and therefore enables quick drying of the specimens. Furthermore, the specimens can be pinned without any problems. Alternatively, small pieces of white (acid-free) cloth like Kleenex may be used. Never use recycled (acidic) material for stuffing.

Fig. 4. Hemp fibres, entire and cut (right hand side). Foto Lisa Schäublin.

2) Cutting the body

Using fine scissors, the inter-segmental skins of the abdomen are cut open on the left side (Fig. 5). Make sure that the subgenital plate (the apical abdominal plate) will not be injured!

Fig. 5. Cutting the body of a bush cricket (*Tettigonia viridissima*).

3) *Void the abdomen*

With a fine pair of pincers the entrails are completely removed (Fig. 6). Using the forceps, first penetrate far into the thorax, grasp the gut and pull it out together with the rest of the intestinal tract. Cut off the rectum shortly before the end, do not tear it off. Then remove the remaining intestines. Do not injure the inside of the skin. The intestines can be stored separately as a liquid preparation. Since the specimen and the accompanying visceral organs are stored separately, they must both be labelled with a unique code (e.g., a GBIF barcode label) and the complete location information!

Fig. 6. Removing entrails from a bush cricket. Foto Lisa Schäublin.

4) *Drying the body cavity*

The remaining body fluid is absorbed with an absorbent cloth (Fig. 7). The body fluid is usually colourless or yellowish. If it turns brownish (as in the picture!), this is a sign that the preparation was started too late and decomposition has already started. This can destroy the delicate colours, hence the specimens should be stuffed immediately after killing.

Fig. 7. Drying the body cavity of a bush cricket. Foto Lisa Schäublin.

5) *Stuffing the body cavity*

The resulting hollow is filled with the finely cut hemp fibres (Fig. 8) and brought into its original shape. First push the hemp as far forward as possible into the thorax, which has to be filled rather tightly to achieve the necessary stability for needling. Stuff also the abdomen, as it shrinks by about 5–10% when drying. Then join the cut edges together. If possible, do not injure the inner side of the skin.

Fig. 8. Filling the body cavity of a bush cricket with hemp fibres. Foto Lisa Schäublin.

6) *Pinning the specimen*

After stuffing, a stainless-steel insect pin of size 1–5, is inserted through the pronotum at the back right (Fig. 9). The strength of the insect pin depends on the size of the specimen. Basically the pins should not be too thin, e.g. a small grasshopper may still be pinned with a pin no. 1–2, while a large bush-cricket should at least get a no. 4 pin.

Fig. 9. Pinning of a bush cricket through the right hand side of the pronotum. Foto Lisa Schäublin.

7) *Fixing the position on the pin*

The correct height on the pin is best determined with a pinning block (Fig. 10). The pin should stick out no more 1 cm at the top.

Fig. 10. Determining the correct height of a bush cricket on the pin with the pinning block (Etikettentreppe). Foto Lisa Schäublin.

8) *Arranging the appendages*

With two dissecting pins the extremities are brought into the desired position on the pinning block (Fig. 11). A polystyrene or peat board about 3 cm thick is suitable for that purpose.

Fig. 11. Arranging antenna and legs of a bush cricket. Foto Lisa Schäublin.

9) The position of the extremities

Normally, the extremities are fixed as close to the body as possible with a few pins. In this way, specimens do not take up unnecessary space in the collection (Fig. 12). The sensitive extremities are also well protected and do not break off as easily.

Fig. 12. Mounted bush crickets (*Barbitistes serricauda*). Antenna and legs should be arranged closely to the body, similar to the eight specimens on the right hand side. Foto Lisa Schäublin.

10) *Arranging the wings*

If required, the wings can be spread on the left side. The wings are fixed all around with the help of transparent paper strips, but not pierced (Fig. 13). A block of soft wood is suitable as a base for the wings.

Fig. 13. Arranging the wings of bush crickets. Foto Lisa Schäublin.

11) The "quick and dirty" genitalia preparation for bush crickets

In case of crickets and bush-crickets the internal genital organs (the titillators) are removed and mounted on a card rectangle (Fig. 14A). Pull out the titillators from behind with fine tweezers and cut them off from the remaining tissue. Transfer the sample to ethanol 60% and carefully remove soft tissue under the stereomicroscope. Drain the titillators on tissue and stick them with insect glue on a card rectangle, which is attached to the pin directly below the specimen (Fig. 14B).

Fig. 14A. Titillators (part of the male genital organs of a bush cricket) glued on a card rectangle. Foto Hannes Baur.

Fig. 14B. Position of card rectangle with titillators on the pin. Foto Hannes Baur.

12) The "quick and dirty" genitalia preparation for grasshoppers

In the case of grasshoppers, expose the genital apparatus. In many species (e.g., of the genera *Miramella* or *Calliptamus*) it is completely sufficient to pull the skin backwards over the genital apparatus to expose the taxonomically important aedeagus (15A, 15B).

Fig. 15A (left), *Miramella alpina* with male genitalia exposed. B (right), genitalia, detail. Fotos Hannes Baur.

13) Drying

Leave the mounted specimen (Fig. 16) in a well ventilated, dry and dark place at room temperature for several days, or place it in an hot cupboard at 40–50°C for 1–2 days. On longer excursions the shelf under the windscreen in a car may replace the warming cupboard.

Fig. 16. Bush cricket drying on pinning block for a few days. Foto Lisa Schäublin.

Mounting specimens on card rectangles

A large part of insects is either too small or otherwise unsuitable for being pinned directly, for example most beetles, bugs, earwigs, and parasitic wasps.

Such specimens may be glued on card rectangles. The procedure is simple:

- 1) Kill specimens in vapour of ethyl acetate (as above).
- 2) Glue specimen with the lower side (or lateral side in the case of parasitic wasps) on a standard card rectangle. Specimens should be glued in the right half of the card with the head pointing to the right.
- 3) Arrange appendages in a way that the important characters are well visible (Fig. 17). Make sure that appendages do not project beyond the card rectangle.
- 4) Mount the card rectangle on an insect pin no. 3 or 4. The pin is pierced through the left fifth of the card, which is put to the upper most level of the pinning block.

Fig. 17. Ground beetles mounted on card rectangles in a Carabidae collection (NMBE). In some specimens, the male genitalia, mounted on a plastic sheet, are protruding beneath. This kind of double mounting is very popular among Coleopterists. Foto Max Reinhard.

Further reading

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